

TYPICAL MISTAKES OF FOREIGN STUDENTS WHEN LEARNING LATIN AND WAYS TO ELIMINATE THEM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7698143>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 25-fevral 2023 yil

Ma'qullandi: 28-fevral 2023 yil

Nashr qilindi: 03-mart 2023 yil

KEY WORDS

Latin language; teaching in English; medical terminology; term elements; aphorisms; motivation; general cultural development.

ABSTRACT

This article deals with the issue of teaching Latin in English in a medical school. The purpose of this discipline is to train terminologically competent doctors. It explains the details of teaching Latin in English, the difficulties that arise in the process of teaching Latin to foreign students, and how to overcome them. Particular attention is paid to how to optimize the learning process and increase motivation.

Following global educational trends, many major universities in Uzbekistan offer education in English. In 2019, for the first time, an English language program was introduced at our university on the basis of a medical institute. Students from different countries take courses in the specialties "General Medicine, Dentistry, Pediatrics, Medical Prevention, Traditional Medicine".

Latin is a completely new subject for first-year students who have never studied it before, which creates a certain difficulty in learning. In medical universities, Latin is taught to familiarize students with the basics of studying and using medical terminology, not only at the university, but also in their subsequent professional activities, that is, to train linguistically literate doctors. [2]. Since Latin is a field of pedagogy, it is most directly related to all areas studied in medical school, especially anatomy, biology, biochemistry, microbiology, pharmacology and clinical areas.

Main part

Teaching Latin in English causes certain difficulties, especially for those students for whom it is not native. When studying the Latin language, special attention is paid to memorizing terms. Many words in English denoting terms are of Greek-Latin origin, so mastering them is not difficult for a person who speaks English well. The situation is different for students whose native language is Arabic or Chinese. In these languages, similar words can be completely different. Students have to spend more time memorizing them. The situation is even more tense with foreign students with poor language skills. It happens that they do not know many English words, and the teacher has to spend more time explaining this or that term. The lexical minimum required for mastering the discipline (in the amount of 900 units) is intended for lasting memorization at the level of long-term memory. These are words and term elements selected according to the principle of frequency of use, thematic importance

and word-formation valence [Ibid.]. To facilitate memorization, the teacher can use the method of associative links, for example: the word *gaster* [stomach] can be remembered using the familiar word *gastritis*. Learning words is an integral part of the Latin language classes. Students start special notebooks for writing down new words. Keeping notebooks is regularly checked. Words are learned in dictionary form, which helps with grammar exercises. Unlike Russian students, foreign students hardly fulfill the requirements of the teacher, sometimes they can afford not to learn the necessary material, forget the notebook, textbook. As a result, the Latin language begins to seem complicated and uninteresting. After conducting a survey among students about the difficulties of learning Latin, it was revealed that for many of them the main problems are: a large amount of time spent on cramming, and a language barrier due to poor knowledge of the English language.

Teaching Latin in a medical school does not require the study of a large amount of grammatical material. Here you will only touch on the aspects necessary to build and understand anatomical terminology (nominative and genitive singular and plural in declensions of Latin nouns and adjectives) in order to develop your recipe writing skills. Attach (mandatory verb form, sentence control). However, foreigners with poor language skills find it difficult to deal with grammatical divisions such as inflection, person, and case. Memorizing words in dictionary form helps us to speak not only about the lexical content of a word, but also about some of its grammatical parameters. Includes regular exercise practice. Pupils like individual work on cards, computer tests. Dictations and oral surveys with new words are also forms of ongoing monitoring of the assimilation of the material.

The study of clinical terminology included in the course does not require the active use of grammatical material. Students are required to memorize the terminological elements of Greek-Latin origin, which underlie the formation of medically significant terminology. Clinical terms refer to "various objects, processes and phenomena associated with the prevention, diagnosis and differentiation of diseases, methods of examining patients, methods of treatment, etc." [3, p. 165]. Students should know and understand that knowledge of medical terminology and the ability to use it are an integral part of the professional competence of future doctors. At the same time, teachers face the challenge of helping students understand the structure of terms and their constituents, as well as teaching them how to construct and understand their own meanings. Each lesson introduces new elements that are part of the terminology. Numerous training exercises can improve function and enhance memory. Students complete the task of defining common meanings and creating clinical terms in accordance with the elements of the term. In this regard, the presence of a dictionary at the end of the textbook is very useful.

Learning pharmaceutical terminology is also important for medical students. It includes the nomenclature of medicines used in the pharmaceutical market. Students get acquainted with some terms in order to have an idea of how their names are created, learn to isolate frequency segments in the composition of drug names that carry certain typical information about the drug. Mastering the skills of writing recipes involves knowing the structure of the recipe, standard recipe formulations and grammatical forms of the parts of speech used. Learning the Latin names of chemical elements and compounds will be useful when studying other special disciplines, such as biochemistry, pharmacology, etc. Unfortunately, the number of hours for learning Latin is critically small. In this regard, the third part of the course is

studied at a fast pace and involves a lot of independent work of students.

In addition to medical terminology, the classes also pay attention to Latin aphorisms and popular expressions, which help not only to learn centuries-old wisdom, but also to better memorize Latin words. At each lesson, the student is asked to memorize one or two aphorisms, which, to a certain extent, "revive" the study of a "dead" language. Some aphorisms of the Latin language relate to issues of life and death (*Vivere militare est. / To live is to fight*), human health (*Hygiena amica valetudinis. / Hygiene is a friend of health*), the behavior of a doctor (*Medice, cura aegrotum, sed non morbum. / Doctor, treat the patient, not the disease*), are medical commandments (*Salus aegroti suprema lex medicorum. / The good of the patient is the highest law of doctors; Primum noli nocere! / First of all, do no harm!*) [3]. Thus, the problem of general cultural development of the student is also solved.

A special role in the study of the Latin language in a medical school is played by increasing the motivation of students' educational and cognitive activity. The teacher must constantly remind the student that the knowledge and skills gained in the study of the Latin language will be widely applied in subsequent courses, in the course of studying special disciplines. This is facilitated by the integration between the Latin language course, on the one hand, and the medico-theoretical and clinical disciplines, on the other hand. The teacher, introducing anatomical terms and explaining the grammar rules used in their construction, can mention their occurrence in the anatomy course. In anatomy atlases, all words have Latin names. The names of the disciplines studied by medical students are also of Greek-Latin origin (biology - the science of life, cardiology - the science of the heart, cytology - the science of cells, etc.). When students in classes in other disciplines begin to easily understand scientific terminology, built on the Latin roots already familiar to them and according to the rules of Latin word formation, they are constantly convinced of the usefulness and necessity of Latin for their own education. Some words heard from doctors are now becoming clear. A medical student proudly realizes that he is mastering a special language of doctors that is inaccessible to people of other specialties.

To optimize the teaching of students in Latin in English, new methods are being actively introduced. Grammar and lexical material is carefully developed, exercises are used that develop the logic of thinking, consciousness and literacy in the use of terms, free orientation in various subsystems of medical terminology. Analysis of the results of independent and control work allows both the teacher and students to identify difficulties in mastering the material and eliminate them. In addition to written work, an oral survey is regularly conducted to check the assimilation of vocabulary, as well as tasks performed at home or in class. The form of final control is a test.

Conclusion

Teaching Latin in English has its own characteristics, connected both with overcoming the language barrier for some students, and with the organization of the learning process and knowledge control. Many students do not make it a rule to regularly attend classes and do their homework. In this regard, the learning process slows down and not all students have the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities by the end of the course. Teaching in English requires more work, patience, attention and energy expenditure on the part of the teacher. He has to pay more attention to discipline and educational conversations.

So, the study of Latin is an integral part of the training of future doctors. Whether this

discipline is taught in Russian or English, the goal remains the same - to create the basis for the terminological system of a professional language. Of course, the conceptual content of terms can be fully and strictly disclosed only when studying special disciplines in the relevant departments. Successful study of the Latin language will only contribute to their easier assimilation and application.

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